

Architecture of Collaboration

Open Source as a Driving
Force for Polish Innovation
and Technological Sovereignty

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1. Introduction

1.1. Goals of the Study and Project

As we present this report to you, the discussion on Poland’s digital sovereignty is rapidly gaining momentum. With it come conversations about the understanding of the open-source concept, which is crucial to this topic.

The purpose of the study “Architecture of Collaboration. Open Source as a Driving Force for Polish Innovation and Technological Sovereignty” was to describe the Polish open-source landscape – including its communities, initiatives, and specific solutions – and to define the role of the Polish administration in activities supporting free and open-source software.

We analyzed the factors supporting the development of open source solutions and the barriers to their implementation – structural (technological), mindset-related (resulting from prejudices or stereotypes), as well as those related to business models and management. An essential element of the work was mapping positive examples of the use of open-source software (OSS) and open-source hardware (OSH) abroad to serve as a collection of best practices from which the Polish market and public administration can draw. The collected data and conclusions from other analyses were used to identify specific directions and implementation paths, as well as to formulate recommendations that can be adopted to leverage the potential of open-source solutions more effectively and, indirectly, to enhance Poland’s digital sovereignty.

The study was conducted as part of the Tech Sovereignty Task Force PL project, which comprises the Panoptykon Foundation, CoopTech Hub (CTH), and the Centrum Cyfrowe Foundation. The project’s goal is to understand the current situation and strengthen the community that creates and uses open-source solutions in Poland.

1.2. Context: Digital Crossroads and the Sovereignty Gap

Our digital landscape is at a turning point. Poland is striving to position itself as a digital leader in Central and Eastern Europe, but this advancement remains reliant on infrastructure over which we do not have full, or even majority, control. **The operating systems, analytical tools, and communication platforms that drive our economy, public administration, institutions, and education system are mostly owned by a narrow circle of global corporations, are subject to foreign jurisdictions, and serve the private interests of vendors and shareholders.** An increasing dependence on these service providers, geopolitical tensions expanding into the

digital sphere, and the pressure to rapidly automate public services mean that merely talking about these dependencies is no longer enough. Tangible alternatives are needed.

Today, as more and more public services are automated and artificial intelligence systems become intermediaries between the state and its citizens, the question of who exercises control over infrastructure, tools, and data (including sensitive and personal data) is no longer a purely technical issue. It is a question of the safety and security of citizens, of Poland's sovereignty, and of the resilience of our economy and society against geopolitical turmoil. Also crucial is the attitude of the members of the Polish OSS developer community – their beliefs, sense of agency, and the real power of their voice in the global exchange of ideas. This sentiment was echoed by an expert during an in-depth interview:

"After last year's FOSDEM, I was looking through [the program] – at that two-day conference, there were about 900 speakers. From what I recall, it turned out there were only about 15 Polish presenters, which is very few for such a large number and most of them were actually living abroad. [...] Aren't we paying the price now for the fact that, early on, we wanted to develop quickly, so we focused on subcontracting? And then there is our typical Polish mindset regarding the West: 'they probably know better, so let's not interfere; let them do it for us, and we will just use it for free because we are still catching up.' I hope I am wrong." (IDI)

This is also a matter of adapting the strategy to contemporary challenges and the current legislative landscape. At the beginning of June 2026, the European Commission announced a package of measures to support open-source software: from the so-called [Chips Act 2.0](#) (addressing the urgent need for European markets to achieve independence in semiconductor supply), through the [Cloud and AI Development Act](#) (defining the framework through which the computing power of European data centers will triple) and [Open Source Strategy](#)¹, which is fundamental to the economic resilience of European Union member states, to the European office suite – [office.eu](#), built on Nextcloud².

In Poland, the Ministry of Digital Affairs has also initiated efforts recognizing the important role of open-source software and hardware. The principles and values of open source have been included among the objectives defined in the "[State Digitalization Strategy until 2035](#)"³. In April 2026, a ministerial order was issued establishing a task force for the development, dissemination, and implementation support of open-source solutions in the public sector ⁴. A month later, the Ministry launched open public consultations titled "Digital Future in Your Hands"⁵, which included discussions on free and open-source software (FOSS). From this

1 European Commission, *Commission proposes tech sovereignty package to strengthen Europe's digital autonomy and resilience*, 2026, https://ec.europa.eu/commission/press-corner/detail/en/ip_26_1187.

2 Office EU, FAQ, <https://office.eu/faq>.

3 Ministry of Digital Affairs, *Realizacja strategii cyfryzacji państwa*, 2026, <https://www.gov.pl/web/cyfryzacja/strategia-cyfryzacji-panstwa>.

4 Ministry of Digital Affairs, *Zarządzenie Nr 5 Ministra Cyfryzacji z dnia 17 kwietnia 2026 r. w sprawie utworzenia Zespołu do spraw rozwoju, upowszechniania i wsparcia wdrażania w sektorze publicznym rozwiązań typu open source*, 2026, <https://www.gov.pl/web/cyfryzacja/du-mc-poz-9>.

5 Ministry of Digital Affairs, *Cyfrowa przyszłość w Twoich rękach - zapraszamy do udziału w konsultacjach społecznych*, 2026, <https://www.gov.pl/web/baza-wiedzy/cyfrowa-przyszlosc-w-twoich-rekach---zapraszamy-do-udzialu-w-konsultacjach-spoecznych>.

perspective, in-depth analyses and meticulous research into the issue of OSS within the Polish context are not only important but also urgent. We hope that this report will shed light on the current state of affairs and encourage questions and discussions that go beyond those raised in the following pages.

Our study reveals an “archipelago effect” – the existence of isolated grassroots initiatives that lack representation within public administration circles. This leaves a vacuum, often filled by corporate monopolies and superficial posturing toward openness, which our respondents explicitly describe as “open-washing.” However, new grassroots projects (especially in the field of AI, such as SpeakLeash and Bielik AI) demonstrate the power of local, auditable innovation, and the working group at the Ministry of Digital Affairs may signal a shift toward strategic institutionalization.

1.3. Research Methodology

The project was conducted using a complementary methodological approach, combining desk research with qualitative in-depth interviews (IDIs). We conducted 15 interviews with experts active in the fields of open-source software, public administration, new technologies, and artificial intelligence. **The individuals we spoke with represent a wide spectrum of the OS community – including software developers, professionals from non-governmental organizations, state and local government entities, commercial companies, research and academia.** The respondents have direct experience in developing and implementing open solutions in organizations and companies, supported by their participation in national and international projects, and they are also involved in the research, development, and commercialization of these technologies. This diversity of perspectives allowed us to enrich the analysis with often divergent, yet frequently complementary visions of the development of open-source software in Poland. In the text below, conclusions and quotes from the interviews conducted are designated as “IDI,” without indicating a specific person or interview number, in order to maintain the anonymity of the experts. Selected quotes have been edited for linguistic correctness and readability, while care was taken to preserve the original meaning and context of the statements.

The analysis of the interviews was conducted manually, whereas the desk research relied on a combination of AI tools (NotebookLM and Gemini) and manual analysis. All conclusions, the structure of the report, the content, and the substantive core are the sole responsibility of the authors; AI tools were employed only for the initial editing and organization of the content. A working translation of the report was prepared using large language models (LLMs), but the final editing (in both Polish and English) was carried out without automated assistance.

2. What is Open Source?

Understanding the potential of open-source software requires a precise definition of this field at the outset. In public debate, “open source” is sometimes mistakenly reduced solely to free alternatives to commercial software. The interviews conducted with experts clearly show that **the ways of defining this concept are diverse: ranging from strict technical standards, code transparency, licensing agreements, and user autonomy, to collaborative frameworks, core values, ideology, and the execution of digital sovereignty and state security policies.**

Crucially, the modern internet and state infrastructure would stop functioning without open-source solutions. As our respondents note, most of the systems we use every day – from search engines to video transcoding algorithms on large-scale platforms – rely on open libraries (e.g., Chromium, FFmpeg) developed over the years by global communities. There are well-documented accounts of individual engineers who dedicate their free time to working pro bono to maintain components crucial to the functioning of a major part of our technical infrastructure. Sometimes this work is so burdensome that it leads to burnout, thereby creating a dangerous situation where strategic components of the entire technological stack remain without real support or oversight.

Widely used tools and technologies, such as Linux, Python, Firefox, and LibreOffice, have been built on an open model. **The paradox is that the average internet user – and often political decision-makers or public officials – rarely realize that they are leveraging open technology merely wrapped in a commercial brand.** This “transparency” of open source means it is treated like air – and no one thinks about it, as long as it works as it should. In reality, however, tech giants (Big Tech) build their billion-dollar empires using open code as a free foundation on which they superimpose their own closed and proprietary layers. This phenomenon creates a fundamental asymmetry: on the one hand, open-source solutions drastically lower the barrier to entry for innovation and allow for rapid digital development, while on the other hand, they relieve commercial entities of the cost of creating core technologies, often without offering much in return to the global community.

2.1. Open Code – Not Just a Technical Matter

As can be read on the Polish government’s website: “Open-source software is referred to as ‘open software.’ This means that the code used to build the program is publicly available. Such software can be legally used, distributed, and modified under the terms specified in the license. The purpose of open source is precisely to enable everyone to develop and improve

it, while respecting copyright.⁶ **Therefore, when discussing open code, we are inherently referring to open-source software. Source code is not a mere add-on to software, but its very essence – it is what software is comprised of, and its characteristics determine whether a technology is truly open.**

Though the public availability of code is the foundation, specialized international organizations, such as the Open Source Initiative (OSI), list ten specific criteria that must be met by software distribution terms to be considered truly open-source⁷. In addition to the right to free redistribution, the absence of usage restrictions, and a license allowing for modifications and derivative works, these standards categorically prohibit any discrimination against persons, groups, or fields of activity (meaning the code must be equally available to businesses, research/academia, and public administration alike).. Furthermore, these licenses must be technologically neutral and automatic – rights to the code belong to each subsequent user without the need to sign additional contracts. In practice, this means that under this definition, open source is not merely a technical aspect of file sharing, but a standard that guarantees that once opened, the code will remain an independent and secure common good⁸.

“Open source is like showing the inner workings of any project. [...] We understand open source as a general operating principle that our sources should be available and usable. The entire process of knowledge creation should be capable of being realized, reproduced, adapted.” (IDI)

2.2. Open And Free Software: Philosophy of Co-Creation and Equality

For the experts participating in our study, **open-source software is not just a matter of code, but a comprehensive approach to creation through collaboration.** This means that the code does not belong to one particular person or company – it is open, public, and “*simply a kind of philosophy of life, sharing what has been developed as an individual for the common good*” (IDI).

This approach is identical to the tradition of free software based on four fundamental user freedoms: the freedom to run, study, modify, and share the software⁹. The concept of free software places the human being and their rights at the center, rather than the code – ensuring the right for technology to serve them rather than control them. This is an ethical perspective, not just a technical one. In the interviews, our respondents readily described open source through the lens of values, community, and justice – referring to an approach to OSS where user freedom is the starting point, not a derivative of licensing criteria.

6 Ministry of Digital Affairs, *Oprogramowanie open source*, 2026, <https://www.gov.pl/web/koduj/oprogramowanie-open-source>.

7 Open Source Initiative, *The Open Source Definition*, 2006 (ostatnia aktualizacja: 2024), <https://opensource.org/osd>.

8 It is precisely because open and free software is understood as a common good that in this report we use the term “open source” (in lowercase), rather than “Open Source”, unless this phrase is used in the context of a specific solution, regulation, or initiative.

9 Free Software Foundation Europe, *What is Free Software*, <https://fsfe.org/freesoftware/freesoftware.en.html>.

2.3. Open Licenses and Access

The technical understanding of open source has recently gained ground in EU law. In recitals 17. and 18. of the [Cyber Resilience Act \(CRA\)](#), the European Parliament and the Council of the European Union treat “free and open-source software” as a single, consistent legal standard, without separating the technical dimension from licensing. According to this definition, code openness exists only when the license guarantees users the four specific freedoms mentioned above: free access, use, modification, and redistribution¹⁰. The interpretation of these provisions is critical – specifically, whether these four freedoms are inalienable or if they can be rescinded from subsequent links in the supply chain. This is where the line is drawn between two completely different market approaches and methods of licensing open-source software:

- **Permissive licenses** (e.g., MIT, Apache 2.0) guarantee the four basic rights to the initial developer, but allow them to be rescinded from subsequent users. A commercial company can legally take open code, modify it, and, upon redistribution, close the source code and monetize it as its own proprietary product. For businesses, this is a powerful lever, but for public administration, it carries the risk of vendor lock-in.
- **Licenses based on the reciprocity principle** (so-called copyleft, such as the GPL) guarantee that the four basic rights are passed down indefinitely. Anyone who modifies or distributes such code is under an absolute obligation to guarantee the same four freedoms to all subsequent creators and users, making it impossible for corporations to “appropriate” the technology.

Beyond these, there are other licensing approaches, and the choice comes down to legal and technical nuances:

- **Weak copyleft** (e.g., LGPL, MPL): This is the “happy medium.” It allows businesses to combine open code with proprietary code (which appeals to developers) while obligating them to return any improvements made to the base component back to the community.
- **Strong network copyleft** (e.g., AGPL): Designed specifically with cloud systems (SaaS) in mind, it mandates opening the source code if the program is modified and made available to users over the internet.
- **Public domain** (e.g., CC0): This is an extreme example of the permissive approach. The author waives all rights, and the code becomes a purely common good – allowing anyone to do virtually anything with it.

2.4. From Philosophy to Sovereignty: Open Source in the Times of Hybrid Wars

In an era of profound geopolitical tensions and the rapid advancement of artificial intelligence, [open source is evolving from a social utopia into a critical tool for state security and](#)

¹⁰ Official Journal of the European Union, *Regulation (EU) 2024/2847 of the European Parliament and of the Council of 23 October 2024 on horizontal cybersecurity requirements for products with digital elements and amending Regulations (EU) No 168/2013 and (EU) 2019/1020 and Directive (EU) 2020/1828 (Cyber Resilience Act) (Text with EEA relevance)*, 2024, <https://eur-lex.europa.eu/legal-content/EN/TXT/?uri=CELEX%3A32024R2847>.

building strategic advantage. For the surveyed experts, technological openness has become the foundation of digital sovereignty, defined as the capacity for self-determination and tangible control over critical state infrastructure:

“Generally, what we call digital independence, digital freedom, or digital security [...] is, to me, what open source represents today. In fact, it is something that gives you, as a citizen of a given country – provided, of course, the state invests in it – greater freedom and a sense of agency. It means we can deploy a digital service ourselves, without depending on an external power that can quickly cut us off, which unfortunately happens quite often nowadays. So, what was once an ideology is now more like a... unfortunately, it is likely a political weapon.” (IDI)

From this perspective, free software becomes a tangible defensive shield, and the ability to control it guarantees state stability during crises. As another respondent noted, *“with free software, this control and freedom remain with the user and the public administration”* (IDI).

This ensures independence from the decisions of foreign policymakers, politicians, and the shareholders of global corporations.

What began with code transparency and exposing the inner workings of projects, and subsequently developed through a libertarian movement of cooperative knowledge sharing, has now become a strategic resource and a common good utilized by practically all citizens – even if unconsciously.

3. Review of Public Policies and Regulations

The analysis of public policies and regulations regarding open-source software (OSS) and hardware (OSH) demonstrates their evolution from niche technical solutions to the very foundation of digital sovereignty and modern public administration¹¹. **States support this model for three primary reasons: economic (cost savings and the avoidance of vendor lock-in), political (transparency that builds trust, as well as geopolitical independence), and technical (enhanced security through auditability)**¹².

There is no uniform, global approach to open source; it depends, among other things, on the local context, including the legislative framework. Countries across the European Union, North America, and South America focus on implementing OSS within the public sector. In parts of Asia (such as China and South Korea), it is treated as a tool for building industrial and economic power¹³. The leader in open source within the EU is France¹⁴, where code developed by the public administration holds the status of a public document. Italy imposes a legal requirement for a comparative analysis before purchasing proprietary solutions¹⁵, while Germany invests in infrastructure stability through the Sovereign Tech Agency¹⁶. Against this backdrop, Poland's performance has plenty of room for improvement: there is a lack of systemic guidelines, a dedicated coordinating unit, and lasting results from working group activities, resulting in fragmented efforts. However, the first signs of change at the government level are visible: the Ministry of Digital Affairs – together with the Centre for Information Technology (Centralny Ośrodek Informatyki) – conducted a study on the use of open source in public administration¹⁷ and established a task force dedicated to the development, dissemination, and implementation support of open solutions in the public sector¹⁸.

Notably, Poland serves as an observer of the DC-EDIC¹⁹ (Digital Commons European Digital Infrastructure Consortium), a specialized body established by the European Commission at the end of 2025. Software developed within the framework of DC-EDIC projects will be made available by default under “Free and Open-Source” licenses, and the consortium's plans until 2027 include launching a “One-Stop-Shop” expert hub, organizing a Digital Commons Forum, and publishing an annual report on the state of Europe's digital sovereignty.

11 European Commission, *The impact of Open Source Software and Hardware on technological independence, competitiveness and innovation in the EU economy*, 2021, p. 18, <https://digital-strategy.ec.europa.eu/en/library/study-about-impact-open-source-software-and-hardware-technological-independence-competitiveness-and>.

12 Ibid, p. 16-17, 221-226.

13 Ibid.

14 Ibid, p. 239.

15 Ibid, p. 247-248.

16 Linux Foundation Europe, *Open Source as Europe's Strategic Advantage. Trends, Barriers, and Priorities for the European Open Source Community amid Regulatory and Geopolitical Shifts*, 2025, p. 6, <https://www.linuxfoundation.org/research/world-of-open-source-eu-2025>.

17 Centre for Information Technology (Centralny Ośrodek Informatyki), *Open Source vs Oprogramowanie komercyjne w instytucjach publicznych*, 2019, <https://www.gov.pl/web/popcwsparcie/praktyczne-poradniki>.

18 Ministry of Digital Affairs, *Zarządzenie Nr 5 Ministra Cyfryzacji z dnia 17 kwietnia 2026 r. w sprawie utworzenia Zespołu do spraw rozwoju, upowszechniania i wsparcia wdrażania w sektorze publicznym rozwiązań typu open source*, 2026, <https://www.gov.pl/web/cyfryzacja/du-mc-poz-9>.

19 NGI Commons, *Digital Commons EDIC takes shape with more countries, director and first projects*, 2026, <https://commons.ngi.eu/2026/04/01/digital-commons-edic-takes-shape-with-more-countries-director-and-first-projects/>.

At the same time, the OSS ecosystem has been included in new legal frameworks introduced in the European Union – primarily the Cyber Resilience Act (CRA), which defines the role of an “OSS steward,” imposing responsibility on entities supporting project development to report vulnerabilities and develop security policies²⁰. Meanwhile, the AI Act promotes openness as a tool for building trust and combating bias in artificial intelligence systems. Experts point out that fully leveraging the potential of open source requires systemic changes, particularly regarding institutionalization. This includes, for example, the creation of Open Source Program Offices (OSPOs) in public administration and academia, the launch of EU-level funds modeled after Germany’s Sovereign Tech Fund²¹, the inclusion of OSS-related competencies in official curricula and qualification frameworks²², and the explicit consideration of the Total Cost of Ownership (TCO) of software, rather than being guided solely by license prices²³.

²⁰ Linux Foundation, *Pathways to Cybersecurity Best Practices in Open Source*, 2025, p. 12, https://www.linuxfoundation.org/hubfs/LF%20Research/lfr_cra_031725a.pdf.

²¹ Linux Foundation Europe, *Open Source as Europe’s Strategic Advantage...*, p. 22.

²² European Commission, *The impact of Open Source Software and Hardware...*, p. 22.

²³ *Ibid.*, p. 15.

4. Open Source and Artificial Intelligence

The open-source model in the artificial intelligence (AI) and machine learning (ML) sector has evolved from a technical alternative into a strategic foundation for sovereign AI – that is, models whose dependence on external factors is minimized as much as possible²⁴. Notably, 89% of organizations recognize openness as key to maintaining control over data²⁵, which is essential for ensuring an appropriate level of security and independence from external vendors. Crucially, the open-source movement drives AI development at its very core; open resources (including source code in public repositories) constitute high-quality training data without which the development of market-leading Large Language Models would be impossible.

The Polish open source ecosystem is undergoing a dynamic evolution. “Our” developers are key co-creators of global technological solutions, with contributions spanning both niche libraries and the foundations of the global data science ecosystem. Among projects with global reach, tools that automate programming and analytical tasks stand out. StarCoder²⁶ is revolutionizing code generation leveraging AI, while PandasAI²⁷ introduces an intuitive interface to the most popular data processing library. In the field of browser-based machine learning, DeepLearning.js played a pivotal role by enabling the creation of machine learning models in JavaScript²⁸. The Polish footprint is also evident in libraries recognized as market standards. Although Pandas and GeoPandas are international projects, Polish contributors are responsible for developing key features and optimizing code²⁹. Our developers have also made significant contributions to PyOD (a specialized tool for anomaly detection) and the Orange platform (used for visual data analysis).

In Poland, AI development is driven by strong communities and ambitious grassroots initiatives, such as Bielik AI – one of the most important domestic projects for building open language models (LLMs/SLMs), tailored and attuned to the nuances of the Polish language³⁰. Another example is the TensorFlow Polska group, which brings developers together around this highly popular ML library (originally developed by Google) and supports education and sharing of knowledge³¹.

24 Linux Foundation, *The Essential Role of Open Source in Sovereign AI*, 2025, <https://www.linuxfoundation.org/blog/the-essential-role-of-open-source-in-sovereign-ai>.

25 Linux Foundation Europe, *Open Source as Europe's Strategic Advantage...*, p. 32.

26 ProgramistaJava.pl, *Najciekawsze open source'owe projekty z Polski*, 2025, <https://programistajava.pl/2025/12/18/najciekawsze-open-sourceowe-projekty-z-polski/#Najciekawsze-projekty-open-source-z-Polski-ktore-musisz-znac>.

27 Ibid.

28 Ibid.

29 Ibid.

30 K. Piwowar, A. Tarkowski, M. Owczarek, *AI speaks Polish. The ecosystem of open language models in Poland*, 2024, <https://centrumcyfrowe.pl/en/czytelnia/report-ai-speaks-polish-the-ecosystem-of-open-language-models-in-poland/>.

31 ProgramistaJava.pl, op. cit.

From a European perspective, openness presents an opportunity to level the playing field in the technological race (currently dominated by the USA and China) by pursuing an alternative path of development. France's Mistral demonstrated that open models can compete with proprietary giants, while the EU's OpenEuroLLM project aims to support 35 European languages³². The Chinese-made DeepSeek model series (released in January 2025), proved to be a turning point for the open-source world³³ – chatbots trained specifically to solve multiple stages of tasks have drastically lowered the barrier to entry to advanced AI. While open models guarantee auditability and help combat algorithmic bias³⁴, the industry faces new challenges: “open-washing”³⁵ (i.e., the misuse of the terms “open” or “open source” for models with restrictive licenses) and a hardware barrier – AI development requires massive investments in public GPU/TPU clusters to avoid long-term dependence on cloud providers³⁶.

The EU's [AI Act](#) and the Polish [State Digitalization Strategy](#) are moving toward streamlining processes for creators of open solutions. Proposals include, among other measures, a “fast track” for the regulatory compliance of auditable models and the “public money, public code”³⁷ principle, whereby tax-funded AI is to serve all European innovators³⁸.

32 EuroLLM, *Open EuroLLM Project*, 2026, <https://www.openeurollm.eu/>.

33 Linux Foundation Europe, *Open Source as Europe's Strategic Advantage...*, p. 30.

34 European Commission, *The Impact of Open Source Software and Hardware...*, p. 308.

35 Linux Foundation Europe, op. cit., s. 31.

36 Anastasia Stasenko, *The Will to Generate*, 2026, <https://anastasiastasenko.substack.com/p/the-will-to-generate>.

37 Krajowa Izba Gospodarcza Elektroniki i Telekomunikacji, Feedback to the European Commission's Call for evidence for *European Open Digital Ecosystems*, 2026, https://ec.europa.eu/info/law/better-regulation/have-your-say/initiatives/16213-European-Open-Digital-Ecosystems/F33370614_en, p. 12.

38 Linux Foundation Europe, op. cit., p. 24.

5. Can This be Profitable? Business Models in Open Source Software and Hardware

The open-source ecosystem has developed surprisingly diverse ways of generating economic value, effectively **debunking the myth that source-code openness is incompatible with profitability**. The report, “The Impact of Open Source Software and Hardware on Technological Independence, Competitiveness, and Innovation in the EU Economy,” prepared for the European Commission, identifies eight market-verified business models, illustrating just how broad the spectrum of commercialization opportunities for free and open source software truly is³⁹.

The most common approach is the **auxiliary services model**, where the code is free and revenue is generated through implementation, training, technical support, and consulting. An example of a multibillion-dollar business using this model is Red Hat, the creator of a Linux-kernel-based operating system, which was later acquired by IBM⁴⁰. Nextcloud offers an open-source data storage platform, and its development is funded by the sale of support and consulting services. A similar logic guides the business model of WordPress, a popular website content management system. The platform makes its code openly available while also operating under a **SaaS (Software as a Service) model** that hosts and manages the infrastructure for a fee – the core software can be downloaded and run independently free of charge, while WordPress.com (and dozens of other providers) offer hosting for a fee, thereby relieving individual users of managing a complex technical back-end.

A contrasting approach is the **dual-licensing model**, in which the base version of the software is available under an open license, while an extended version or a commercial license is sold to corporate entities. Oracle’s MySQL operates in precisely this manner: commercial users who do not want to – or cannot – disclose their derivative code can purchase a license that exempts them from the obligations arising from the copyleft principle. Conversely, in the **corporate development and distribution model**, companies fund the developers creating open-source software without expecting a direct return on investment from the code itself. Here, the benefit is strategic: the enterprise leverages an ecosystem it co-creates, sharing maintenance costs with the entire community. This is how, for example, smartphone manufacturers operate by adapting the Android operating system to their own hardware.

³⁹ European Commission, *The impact of Open Source Software and Hardware...*, 2021, p. 54–102.

⁴⁰ *Ibid.*

At the opposite end of the commercialization spectrum lie **models based on community funding, like memberships**. Foundations and umbrella organizations sustain themselves through membership fees from companies and individual developers – the Linux Foundation, for instance, brings together over a thousand corporate members, with no single entity permitted to contribute more than two percent of the total budget, thereby protecting the project’s neutrality⁴¹. **Crowdfunding** goes a step further by relying on voluntary contributions from the general public – platforms such as Patreon and Open Collective enable individual sponsors to regularly support and fund the work of specific developers. **Advertising models** and **update subscriptions** round out these possibilities: Mozilla funds a portion of its operations through agreements with search engines, while the creators of extensions for WordPress or Joomla charge fees for access to regular updates and security patches⁴².

This diversity of models stems from the very nature of open-source software itself, which by design excludes generating revenue solely from license sales, compelling creators to look for added value in other areas. As the authors of “The Impact of Open Source Software and Hardware...” point out, most OSS developers exercise great caution when choosing a business model, rejecting approaches that could negatively affect users – hence the marginal role of **selling user data**, which, while technically feasible, remains rare and carries severe reputational risks within the OSS ecosystem⁴³.

This market flexibility and rich diversity of business models can also be observed in Poland – domestic companies and projects offer a wide range of products and services with various forms of monetization. However, interviews conducted as part of this study strongly echo the opinion that the public administration has not yet developed the mechanisms required to tap into this potential – doing so would require fundamental changes to public procurement frameworks and overcoming internal resistance. The habit of purchasing software as a ready-to-use, “off-the-shelf” product with a license from a specific vendor makes the transition to an open-source model – where organizations pay for implementation expertise, maintenance, and operational guarantees – difficult and complex (see also: [8. Barriers and Risks](#)).

41 Ibid.
42 Ibid.
43 Ibid.

6. What Makes This Work? Components of Success in Open Collaboration Ecosystems

6.1. Community

A key success factor for open-source projects is the community⁴⁴ – without active contributors, even technically perfect code becomes a dead asset. Interpersonal bonds and a people’s willingness to cooperate have a strong impact on how project teams are formed, while the sense of agency and the environment in which a developer begins their journey with a project affect the level and longevity of their commitment^{45, 46, 47}. Established relationships and a position within the group earned through valuable contributions translate into the long-term participation of the individuals involved; furthermore, reduced turnover directly strengthens the project’s resilience⁴⁸. In a community open to collaboration, developers primarily learn from each other, drawing on the diverse experiences of the group’s members⁴⁹.

Importantly, it is not only the core team of active developers that determines project quality – even participants who engage sporadically make a measurable contribution⁵⁰. Nevertheless, active participation pays off – the reputation earned among community members directly influences how code change proposals are treated: the contributions of established individuals are often viewed with greater trust and reviewed more efficiently than those of newcomers⁵¹. Mentoring new community members – introducing them to the communication style, code quality expectations, and discussion culture – proves to be an effective tool for lowering the barrier to entry and integrating potential contributors who might otherwise disengage without such support⁵². Developers’ satisfaction depends on mature leadership, a sense of belonging to a team, and the conviction that their work serves the broader public good⁵³.

44 Ibid, p. 83.

45 J. Hahn et al., *Impact of Social Ties on Open Source Project Team Formation*, 2006, <https://openl.ifip-tc6.org/db/conf/oss/oss2006/HahnMZ06.pdf>.

46 J. Hahn et al., *Emergence of new project teams from open source software developer networks: Impact of prior collaboration ties*, 2008, <https://digitalcommons.memphis.edu/facpubs/11066/>.

47 M. Zhou, A. Mockus, *Who Will Stay in the FLOSS Community? Modeling Participant’s Initial Behavior*, 2015, <https://www.computer.org/csdl/journal/ts/2015/01/06880395/13-RUyYBliq>.

48 Qiu, H. S. et al., *Going farther together: the impact of social capital on sustained participation in open source*. In *Proceedings*, 2019, <https://doi.org/10.1109/ICSE.2019.00078>; in: European Commission, *The impact of Open Source Software and Hardware...*, 2021.

49 P. V. Singh et al., *Network Effects: The Influence of Structural Social Capital on Open Source Project Success*, 2022, <https://doi.org/10.2139/ssrn.1111868>.

50 P. Setia. et al., *How Peripheral Developers Contribute to Open-Source Software Development*, 2012, https://www.researchgate.net/publication/259924766_How_Peripheral_Developers_Contribute_to_Open-Source_Software_Development.

51 A. Bosu, J. C. Carver, *Impact of developer reputation on code review outcomes in OSS projects: an empirical investigation*, 2014, <https://dl.acm.org/doi/10.1145/2652524.2652544>.

52 European Commission, *The impact of Open Source Software and Hardware...*, 2021.

53 L. Chang, *Motivations, Team Dynamics, Development Practices and How They Impact the Success of Open Source Software—A Study of Projects of Code for America Brigades*, 2018, <https://www.semanticscholar.org/paper/Motivations%2C-Team-Dynamics%2C-Development-Practices-Chang/6db2cdf0810839f560f5701c9348ecc3dd3a155>.

The importance of the community is confirmed by quantitative research on the success factors of open source projects. Based on an analysis of 283 projects over a period of three years, researchers Vishal Midha and Prashant Palvia demonstrated that the size of the user base is the strongest predictor of a project's popularity at every stage of its development⁵⁴. They point to the occurrence of a self-reinforcing mechanism here: the more users there are, the more attractive the project becomes to subsequent ones, which the authors interpret through the prism of information cascade theory and Everett Rogers' diffusion of innovations curve⁵⁵. In other words, reaching a critical mass of users in the early stage of development is a factor of fundamental importance for the long-term success of the project⁵⁶.

The relationship between the number of development team members and project success is, in fact, more complex than just that. While the number of active creators positively affects project development at an early stage, in later phases this relationship reverses – a growing team generates coordination and management costs that outweigh the benefits of additional contributors⁵⁷. This suggests that a **healthy OSS community is not so much about having the largest possible number of contributors, as it is about their proper organization: a small, committed core team of developers (responsible for the core codebase), supplemented by a wider community that participates in discussions, testing, and bug reporting**⁵⁸. However, community stability does not automatically guarantee effectiveness. Researchers Param Singh and Yong Tan demonstrated that developers act primarily out of self-interest rather than in the interest of the group⁵⁹ – leading to tensions between the stability and efficiency of the collaborative network. In practice, this means that a community can be durable and cohesive while simultaneously operating below its potential, whether due to being too loosely connected across different types of developers or excessively isolated within homogeneous groups.

In the in-depth interviews conducted as part of this study, we also asked about the characteristics of the community centered on open-source software in Poland. In principle, a "Polish open-source community" can be said to exist – it is characterized by diversity and immense intellectual potential, yet it remains highly fragmented. Although "our" developers have co-created some of the world's most significant projects (e.g., [Linux](#) and [Fedora](#)), their activity at the domestic level resembles an archipelago of isolated islands. **The lack of strong, institutionalized representation means that the voice of the community often goes unheard in dialogue with the public administration, and it is drowned out by large corporations that efficiently and persuasively offer proprietary, off-the-shelf solutions.**

54 V. Midha, P. Palvia, *Factors affecting the success of Open Source Software*, 2012, <https://doi.org/10.1016/j.jss.2011.11.010>.

55 E. Rogers, *Diffusion of Innovations*, 4th ed, 1995.

56 V. Midha, P. Palvia, *op. cit.*

57 *Ibid.*

58 Y. Tan, P. V. Singh, *Stability and Efficiency of Communication Networks in Open Source Software Development*, 2005, <https://doi.org/10.2139/ssrn.886360>; in: V. Midha, P. Palvia, *Factors affecting the success...*, 2012.

59 P. V. Singh, Y. Tan, *Developer Heterogeneity and Formation of Communication Networks in Open Source Software Projects*, 2010, https://papers.ssrn.com/sol3/papers.cfm?abstract_id=1276098.

The core of the open source community in Poland consists of long-established organizations such as the [Polish Linux Users Group \(PLUG\)](#) and the [Reszka Free Software Foundation](#) – the latter’s goal is to provide a professional framework for dialogue with representatives of the public administration and legislative bodies. Hackerspaces (physical bastions of free technical thought, where open-source ideas merge with practice) and gatherings centered around the [Free Software Foundation](#) also play an invaluable role. This grassroots network often intertwines with the activities of organizations fighting for digital rights, such as the [Panoptykon Foundation](#) or [Centrum Cyfrowe](#) (the publisher of this report), creating a broad front for freedom of information. In May 2026, the [Alliance of Friends of Open and Free Software](#) (Sojusz Przyjaciół Otwartego i Wolnego Oprogramowania, SPOIWO) was formed, bringing together social organizations, cooperatives, hackerspaces, collectives, companies, and individual members of the Polish open source community, acting in line with and for the “public money, public code” principle. The Alliance thus demonstrates that it is possible to join forces – even among highly diverse entities – to bolster Polish digital sovereignty.

However, the greatest challenge remaining is the barrier between experts and decision-makers. As two of the interviewees noted:

“Perhaps the state or the ministry wants to talk, but they don’t know with whom – they don’t know who to approach?” (IDI)

“As for the Ministry of Digital Affairs itself, every time open solutions are brought up, I get the impression that they simply cover their ears and say, ‘la la la la la, I can’t hear you, I can’t hear you.’ [...] I notice that the open-source community is out there, but when it comes to the exchange of information between the community and the government, it is an absolute tragedy.” (IDI)

The interviews revealed that the actions of the state administration often resemble so-called “open-washing.” A frequently cited example is the government application mObywatel, where openness applies mainly to the visual layer (the front-end), while the core business logic remains a “black box.” Such factitious transparency provokes resistance from the community, which views it as a wasted opportunity to build genuine citizen trust in the state.

An additional problem is the so-called “brain drain”: the best specialists from Poland are employed by foreign technology companies offering attractive work conditions, which means their work builds corporate value, rather than our local innovation capital. Hope for change is brought by projects such as [SpeakLeash](#) and the Polish language model [Bielik](#)⁶⁰, which unite hundreds of enthusiasts around one, specific goal: Polish AI. However, for this surge not to fade away, it is necessary to move from guerrilla, grassroots initiatives to systemic support

60 See also: K. Piwowar, A. Tarkowski, M. Owczarek, *AI speaks Polish. The ecosystem of open language models in Poland*, 2024, <https://centrumcyfrowe.pl/en/czytelnia/report-ai-speaks-polish-the-ecosystem-of-open-language-models-in-poland/>.

for open source solutions (and communities!) as a fundamental element of building Poland's digital sovereignty.

6.2. Project Management and Governance

Alongside the community, governance is the second key success factor for open collaboration environments. Modern open source projects codify their organizational norms in dedicated files (such as GOVERNANCE.md), which transform unwritten community customs and rules into explicit, verifiable protocols. These documents determine who decides, who does what, and who bears what degree of responsibility⁶¹. As research by Siobhán O'Mahony and Fabrizio Ferraro on the Debian community⁶² shows, a key challenge for open source projects is to develop a shared basis of authority – without it, even smoothly functioning communities can fracture upon their first serious conflict⁶³.

An effective governance model combines two seemingly contradictory elements: formal, hierarchical authority, embedded in project documentation, and democratic mechanisms that keep this authority in check. This requires leaders to act in accordance with the will of the community – their power over technical decisions is limited, and project members also retain the authority to recall a leader from their position. Although these aspects are purely “personal”, rather than “technical,” they are reflected in the project's documentation. This framework typically includes a division into an organizational layer – covering strategy and external relations – and an operational layer focused on day-to-day technical work.

In practice, the codification of rules reveals the so-called “maintainer paradox”: although governance documents define maintainers as technical experts, in reality, they are burdened with a growing mass of organizational and communication tasks, creating a risk of overload and burnout for leaders. Furthermore, the Debian community study shows that meritocracy in open-source ecosystems is an evolving concept – over time, the community increasingly values the organizational competencies of leaders over technical contributions alone, and *merit* encompasses not only code quality but also the ability to sustain the community as a whole⁶⁴. At the same time, **the transparency of the governance system acts as a protective mechanism: constant oversight by the community naturally discourages abuse and aggressive business models.** On a global scale, coordination between projects takes place with the support of umbrella foundations, such as the Linux Foundation, the Apache Software Foundation, or the Eclipse Foundation, which provide neutrality and institutional continuity – making this model a particularly valuable point of reference for the public sector seeking sustainable and democratically managed digital solutions.

61 P. Oliveira et al., *Governance in Practice: How Open Source Projects Define and Document Roles*, 2026, <https://www.semanticscholar.org/paper/Governance-in-Practice%3A-How-Open-Source-Projects-Oliveira-Conte/c1205d0645300da52b780762ac1ffac396e978fd>.

62 S. O'Mahony, F. Ferraro, *The Emergence of Governance in an Open Source Community*, 2007, <https://www.jstor.org/stable/20159914>.

63 Ibid.

64 Ibid.

The emergence of artificial intelligence tools that allow even non-programmers to instantly generate code turned out to be a significant development in not just code creation itself, but OSS project management as well. Moreover, as one of the interviewees noted: *“This barrier to entry into programming, into building tools, and also into the speed of developers’ work has been dramatically lowered [...] Today, first, you have open-source building blocks that are already sitting on the shelves; second, you have a tool that is able to write and implement [the code].”* Incorporating AI models into the continuous integration (CI) pipeline facilitates and accelerates software development. In such a scenario, artificial intelligence theoretically acts as an automated auditor that analyzes source code continuously and provides optimization recommendations.

However, lowering the barrier to entry in this manner comes with certain negative consequences and its own new challenges. A significantly larger volume of (easily generated) code leads to a surge in pull requests – that is, requests to merge new changes into the main project repository. Yet, the process of verifying and testing these submissions still requires the meticulous attention of project participants. Some of these contributions can be extremely valuable – such as improving system performance or patching security vulnerabilities – but isolating these genuine fixes within the influx of unverified code requires an immense amount of time and energy from other community members. Thus, AI can contribute to the cognitive overload and burnout of maintainers, effectively acting as a form of DDoS (Distributed Denial of Service) attacks.

Another issue involves copyright, which raises significant concerns among creators. AI models are trained on massive datasets, including those published in open repositories, such as GitHub. However, many of these publicly available projects are protected by specific licenses, and the copyright status of newly generated AI code remains highly ambiguous: *“There is no certainty whether, after some time, the companies that own these tools will claim copyright over them, forcing us to revert commits [changes]”* (IDI). OSS creators have no certainty regarding the provenance of the data used to train AI. As a result, while AI tools lower the barrier to entry for programmers wonderfully, the mass-generated code multiplies the amount of verification work for those maintaining open-source projects. (Other issues accompanying the development of artificial intelligence, including sovereign AI, are discussed in section [4. Open Source and Artificial Intelligence](#).)

In conclusion, the analysis of the success components and governance structures in international open source projects yields three key insights for the digitalization strategy of the Polish public administration:

1. **The state as a guarantor of a “critical mass”:** Since research demonstrates that the size of the user base is the strongest predictor of a project’s survival, the public administration (including local governments) holds a unique market advantage. The introduction of a systemic requirement to use an open-source solution across hundreds of offices automatically creates a critical mass of users. Consequently, the project gains stability, rendering it attractive to the commercial market and paving the way for subsequent implementations.

2. **Broad community involvement and public procurement:** The optimal organization of work on an open-source project consists of a small, dedicated core team and a broad community forming the testing base. Recognizing this dynamic fundamentally alters the role of the public administration (as in, the commissioning party) in the software development process. The state does not need to hire an army of developers. Instead, the responsibility of central institutions (e.g., NASK or the Ministry of Digital Affairs) should be to fund and oversee the project's core (the core team, code quality, and security audits), while local governments, Polish IT companies, and end users will naturally form a community to test the system in practice.
3. **Institutional mitigation of the "maintainer paradox":** The public administration cannot base critical state systems on grassroots volunteering. Since the codification of rules (governance) and community maintenance generate immense coordination costs that burn out project leaders, the state must assume the role of an umbrella organization to relieve developers of these administrative and financial burdens, thereby guaranteeing the neutrality, continuity, and legal stability of the digital commons (modeled on the Linux Foundation).

7. The Impact of Open Source Software on the Economy

7.1. Costs: Benefits and Ambiguities

The analysis of the impact of open-source software on the economy, conducted at the macro- and microeconomic levels, indicates that its immense value-added far exceeds initial investment costs. At the macro level, it is estimated that in 2018, companies in the European Union invested approximately EUR 1 billion in OSS, while the resulting impact on the European economy reached an estimated EUR 65–95 billion⁶⁵. A 10% increase in open-source contributions would generate an annual increase of 0.4% to 0.6% in the European Union's GDP⁶⁶. At the same time, such an expansion would drive the creation of over 600 new ICT start-ups annually across the EU⁶⁷. Open-source software serves as an infrastructure comparable to highways or bridges, lowering the barrier to market entry and expanding the pool of publicly available knowledge.

However, applying these indicators to the Polish administration and business sectors encounters a major barrier: the cost ambiguity of open-source solutions at the implementation stage. In expert interviews, this ambiguity manifests as a deep fear of the “free software trap.” Decision-makers worry that the lack of licensing fees is merely a financial illusion – one that will be quickly absorbed by dramatically higher system integration costs, the premium required to secure scarce IT specialists, and the operational risks arising from a lack of guaranteed vendor support under service-level agreements (SLAs). This lack of budgetary predictability paralyzes official decision-making, forcing a return to proprietary models where licensing prices, though high, are known upfront. It is crucial to note, however, that familiarity with the baseline license price does not equate to knowing the total cost of ownership (TCO), including implementation, ongoing development, or auxiliary services required during actual use.

“Among many IT giants, the bundling model is highly prevalent. The client is lured by an inexpensive license, but ultimately has to bear immense costs associated with a mandatory training package or the implementation itself, which often exceed the value of the product.” (IDI)

⁶⁵ European Commission, *The impact of Open Source Software and Hardware...*, 2021.

⁶⁶ Ibid.

⁶⁷ Ibid.

To prevent this macroeconomic potential from remaining a purely theoretical model, a holistic, integrated approach at the state level is necessary to rationalize these implementation risks. The primary value lies in avoiding vendor lock-in, where a single provider dictates terms and inflates prices, as switching systems is prohibitively expensive. Open-source software grants the freedom to switch service providers without losing functionality – institutions pay for the actual implementation and development of code for their own use, rather than for the perpetual lease of a license. This is of paramount importance in the context of the trade deficit in digital services, which in 2024 amounted to approximately PLN 45 billion⁶⁸, meaning that a significant portion of software spending permanently left domestic economic circulation in the form of licensing fees paid to foreign vendors.

Transitioning to an open-source model would mean a structural shift in these financial flows – primary costs would shift from being cost-intensive (licensures) to labor-intensive, potentially redirected toward domestic software implementation and IT service companies. For Polish local governments and the SME sector, this would ensure not only reduced reliance on singular technology vendors, but also a more efficient use of public funds. **Solutions commissioned by the state could be made available under open licenses, enabling other public offices, schools, enterprises, and organizations to use, develop, and implement them without incurring the costs of developing duplicate software from scratch.**

Microeconomic benefits also extend to the physical, hardware level. Transitioning to OSS enables organizations to break free from so-called “surveillance capitalism”; applications are lighter, running locally rather than within energy-intensive Big Tech cloud infrastructures, and do not prematurely drain hardware resources (see also: [7.2. Sustainable Development of Open Source Projects](#)).

“We are wasting massive amounts of public money by paying to deploy the same code multiple times. We spend so much on licensing fees that we could actually build something of our own with those funds, and never have to pay again. Unfortunately, I view the current government’s actions as superficial; there is a clear need for more profound change, greater awareness, and less hype-driven action.” (IDI)

7.2. Sustainable Development of Open Source Projects

The sustainable development of open source software and hardware is a multidimensional issue, encompassing both socioeconomic viability and environmental impact. **The foundation of a modern digital economy rests on recognizing free and open-source software as**

⁶⁸ J. Oleszczuk-Zygmuntowski, *Cyfrowy bilans Polski. Jak zmienić uzależnienie w suwerenność?*, 2025, <https://lukasiewicz.gov.pl/cyfrowy-bilans-polski-nowy-raport-centrum-lukasiewicz/>.

critical public infrastructure – the long-term viability of which depends on systemic support for both its widespread adoption, as well as its creators⁶⁹.

The theme of sustainability in the context of OSS can be understood in two ways: from a socioeconomic perspective, which involves the sustainability of the ecosystem (creators and users), and from an environmental perspective – focusing on its efficiency and the lifecycle of physical products within the OSS infrastructure.

Open-source software, devoid of corporate and nonelective telemetry components, features lower resource consumption, enabling applications to operate efficiently without forcing the redirection of processes to expensive external infrastructure owned by foreign vendors. Reduced CPU use and less frequent charging cycles directly extend the lifecycle of these devices. Across the entire administration, this significantly increases the operational utility of computers and servers while reducing both the environmental footprint and the costs of cyclical hardware replacement. The code architecture underlying open-source software inherently promotes energy efficiency. Compiled languages, such as C or Rust (in which the Linux kernel and key open-source tools are written), rank highest in efficiency and memory optimization⁷⁰. Although commercial, proprietary systems (e.g., Windows) also use compiled languages in their core layers, the difference lies in how this code is utilized. Open-source software is modular, and its open architecture allows systems to be configured to execute only the instructions necessary for a given operation. This reduces or eliminates the “software bloat” characteristic of complex proprietary systems. Under the software reuse paradigm, systems can be constructed from precisely selected, independent modules and functions⁷¹, instead of being deployed as indivisible, closed monoliths dependent on a specific vendor (vendor lock-in). Public administrations can deploy open-source systems in minimal configurations tailored to specific administrative tasks, eliminating the waste of hardware resources caused by running unnecessary background processes

The open source model (encompassing OSS and OSH) is a powerful tool for combating planned obsolescence. Access to source code and schematics enables the updating of devices long after the expiration of official manufacturer support, aligning with the principles of the Right to Repair movement and reducing electronic waste⁷². Collaborative development of shared infrastructure (e.g., data centers) eliminates redundant programming efforts, thereby tangibly conserving energy and human resources⁷³.

⁶⁹ Linux Foundation Europe, *Open Source as Europe's Strategic Advantage...*, p. 7.

⁷⁰ R. Pereira, M. Couto, F. Ribeiro, R. Rua, J. Cunha, J. Fernandes, J. Saraiva, *Energy efficiency across programming languages: how do energy, time, and memory relate?*, 2017, p. 256-267.

⁷¹ J. Sametinger, *Software Engineering with Reusable Components*, 1997.

⁷² European Commission, *The impact of Open Source Software and Hardware...*, 2021, p. 20, 75.

⁷³ *Ibid.*

7.3. Underfunding of Open Source Projects as a Systemic Threat

Currently, we can observe a dangerous imbalance: the global internet depends on libraries maintained on a grassroots, voluntary, and informal basis. The Heartbleed vulnerability in OpenSSL (2014) clearly exposed the dangers associated with underfunding – critical code rested on the shoulders of volunteers supporting just a single full-time developer⁷⁴. This situation highlighted how severe the overloading of open-source maintainers can be (see also: [6.2. Project Management and Governance](#)). It is estimated that only 5% of contributors engage on a long-term basis⁷⁵. Although corporations reap billions in profits from OSS, only 28% of them support key projects with full-time staff⁷⁶. However, this does not mean that corporate involvement in these projects is based solely on exploitation. The aforementioned bug was resolved quickly by Google engineers – an intervention made possible solely by the open nature of the code. In the case of closed, proprietary software, there would be no opportunity for such swift support from external specialists.

Viable solutions include mechanisms like GitHub Sponsors or thanks.dev, as well as state initiatives – growing in importance, from the perspective of increasingly pressing matter of digital sovereignty – such as the German Sovereign Tech Fund, which finances maintenance and ensures the stability of open-source foundations⁷⁷.

The future of OSS sustainability is shaped by new legal frameworks, such as the [Cyber Resilience Act](#), which obliges creators to implement a five-year security strategy covering various aspects of a project⁷⁸. The professionalization of management, adopting a symmetric framework (e.g., Nextcloud⁷⁹), facilitates the alignment of community and corporate interests. **Ultimately, a sustainable approach requires shifting from perceiving OSS as “free tools” toward the systemic protection of creators and the responsible, long-term securing of funding for the digital common goods that open-source projects represent⁸⁰.**

74 Ibid, p. 304

75 Ibid, p. 76.

76 Linux Foundation Europe, *Open Source as Europe's Strategic Advantage...*, p. 6.

77 Ibid.

78 Linux Foundation, *Pathways to Cybersecurity...*, p. 24.

79 European Commission, *The impact of Open Source Software and Hardware...*, 2021, p. 71.

80 Linux Foundation Europe, *Open Source as Europe's Strategic Advantage...*, p. 7.

8. Barriers and Risks

A number of systemic barriers stand in the way of implementing open source software in Poland. The transition to open source is not merely a technological problem, but a clash with deeply ingrained (often misguided) beliefs, legal and institutional market arrangements, and structural weaknesses within the OSS creator community itself. In this context, a study published by the Ministry of Digital Affairs, conducted on a sample of $N=604$ public administration units in Poland, is highly interesting. The analysis of licensing practices reveals a deep, almost absolute dependence of the Polish public sector on proprietary and closed solutions – in key areas, such as operating systems or office suites, proprietary software dominates in 98.7% and 91.6% of the surveyed entities, respectively⁸¹.

Among the main obstacles hindering migration to open-source software, decision-makers most frequently cite: rigorous requirements for backward compatibility with commercial systems, deeply ingrained user habits, and cybersecurity concerns arising from a lack of technical support from a specific vendor. At the same time, the study highlights an immense, untapped adaptive potential: in the few technological niches where the administration has adopted ready-made, stable, and free tools – such as geographic information systems (QGIS, accounting for 39.7% of GIS implementations) or graphics software (GIMP, at 36.2%) – open-source solutions successfully compete on a mass scale with the most expensive, closed corporate ecosystems.

8.1. Cybersecurity and Trust Towards Open Code

The openness of source code is often equated with exposing a system to attacks, whereas not disclosing it (known as “security through obscurity”) provides only an illusion of protection. In fact, 73% of experts consider the open source model to be more secure due to its auditability⁸² – open code enables the detection of vulnerabilities and “backdoors,” a matter of critical importance for state systems⁸³.

“Various agencies have stated that making the [mObywatel] code public would be dangerous; if they are right, then whoever originally wrote this code did not anticipate its public release. If making it available were truly a threat, it means the code was written in such a way that security is achieved through secrecy, rather than through inherently secure technical design.” (IDI)

81 Ministry of Digital Affairs, Report of a public institutions study with Centre for Information Technology (Centralny Ośrodek Informatyki), 2026, <https://www.gov.pl/web/cyfrizacja/rozpoczynamy-konsultacje-zalozen-konkursu-na-wdrozenie-open-source>.

82 CRN Polska, *Oprogramowanie open source użyte w Polsce 670 tys. razy*, 2024, <https://crn.pl/aktualnosci/oprogramowanie-open-source-uzyte-w-polsce-670-tys-razy/>.

83 European Commission, *The impact of Open Source Software and Hardware...*, 2021, p. 302.

Properly designed software must guarantee security through its inherent architecture, rather than relying on the secrecy of its structure. Public access to repositories triggers a process of continuous community auditing, in which thousands of independent specialists worldwide continuously scan the code for vulnerabilities. This protects the system from a scenario typical of closed commercial solutions, where a critical vulnerability can remain undetected for years because access to the codebase – and, crucially, the ability to patch it – is restricted to a narrow, closed group of developers or auditors. In light of this, a counterargument may arise that with open-source code, vulnerabilities may be detected by malicious actors seeking to exploit them, rather than patch them. Crucially, however, software bugs accumulate, and seemingly secure, hidden “backdoors” in proprietary software are in reality often known to a wider circle of outsiders, not just the software’s creators⁸⁴. Expanding the group of contributors to include the open source community increases the likelihood of both early detection and rapid remediation.

Regulations such as the Cyber Resilience Act mandate the use of software bill of materials (SBOM; an inventory of components that make up the software), increasing the visibility of dependencies in the supply chain⁸⁵. In Poland, this subject generates an ongoing dispute: official reports (e.g., one accompanying the Digital Poland Operational Programme [Program Operacyjny Polska Cyfrowa]⁸⁶) suggest that code openness threatens the administration, while on the other hand, specialists warn that a lack of openness builds a dangerous dependence on vendors (the previously mentioned vendor lock-in)⁸⁷. It is worth noting here that code openness does not have to mean full transparency of the infrastructure based on open-source software. Technological sovereignty is built in a hybrid model in which commonly available OS solutions form the foundation – code openness guarantees the absence of hidden vulnerabilities and continuous auditing, while the layer containing sensitive elements (e.g., server configuration details, cryptographic keys, or databases) remains isolated and strictly confidential. The means towards trust are Reproducible Builds (which make it possible to check whether a downloaded file or application actually comes from a trusted creator, by verifying the compliance of the compiled binary code with the open source code⁸⁸) and tools like OpenSSF Scorecard⁸⁹.

8.2. Mental Barriers

For decades, the Polish IT sector specialized in providing services outsourced by Western markets, shaping the mentality of a consumer or subcontractor, rather than the attitude of an independent creator of new technologies and innovative, original solutions. One of our interviewees noted that *“it seems like we still have this mindset that we can only use [existing software] and that we are unable to contribute anything of our own to these projects”*. Within

84 Ibid.

85 Linux Foundation, *Pathways to Cybersecurity...*, p. 2.

86 Centre for Information Technology (Centralny Ośrodek Informatyki), *Open Source vs Oprogramowanie komercyjne w instytucjach publicznych*, 2019, <https://www.gov.pl/web/popcwsparcie/praktyczne-poradniki>.

87 European Commission (Open Source Observatory – OSOR), *Open Source Software Country Intelligence Report – Poland*, 2023, p. 4, <https://interoperable-europe.ec.europa.eu/collection/open-source-observatory-osor/open-source-software-country-intelligence>.

88 Linux Foundation, *Pathways to Cybersecurity...*, p. 16.

89 Ibid, p. 19.

public institutions, this passivity is compounded by risk aversion and the desire to shift responsibility onto an external entity. Officials prefer to procure proprietary Big Tech systems because they provide an illusory insurance policy. In the open-source model, organizations must assume responsibility themselves, which breeds fear:

“There is intense pressure to be able to hold someone accountable – and ideally, to pass this responsibility onto someone else. [...] With open source, you take on the responsibility yourself [...], because it’s not as if I can just pick up the phone and complain to Microsoft...” (IDI)

Such a passive attitude is often a consequence of systemic immersion in proprietary solutions. Our habits are shaped as early as during our school years – computer science classes are frequently reduced to a “course” on operating the products of a single vendor, without introducing any alternatives:

“Today, pupils learn Microsoft in schools, and universities teach Microsoft – so when they enter the workforce, it is no wonder that they only see Microsoft as a solution.” (IDI)

Upon entering the labor market, professionals and public service officials replicate this pattern by habit, preferring the commercial systems with which they are familiar. This behavioral pattern is compounded by the high cognitive cost of challenging long-held beliefs and changing habits among employees, as well as the outdated myth that open-source software is unstable or inferior because *“if something is free, yet I’m paying [for another tool], then the free one must be worse”* (IDI). In this context, a significant obstacle is the lack of a clear, systemic precedent from leadership – namely, the central administration. Amid widespread risk aversion, smaller entities and local governments naturally fear the consequences of implementing alternative solutions independently. **Without clear signals and reference implementations at the highest government level, lower-tier decision-makers perceive deviating from commercial standards as risky, prompting them to safely replicate well-worn procurement patterns.**

8.3. Specifics of the Cost Structure

In expert discussions, the subject of “actual costs” often recurs: implementing open-source code is not a one-time licensing expense, but a process requiring continuous expenses on infrastructure maintenance, stable hosting, and – above all – a competent team.

“Personnel is the most expensive component in all of this. Meaning, either having our own team, or paying someone else, external, to come to us.” (IDI)

A lack of long-term planning and financial security leads to projects hitting a budgetary barrier after targeted grants expire. **Even if public entities successfully execute technological projects with the support of earmarked external funds (e.g., EU funds), the key challenge becomes ensuring system continuity once those grants are over.** Without a systemic change in approach to the project lifecycle, even a smoothly operating solution becomes a financial burden over time: *“The project’s sustainability period ends, and now I have a system to maintain. This means I must constantly pay for someone to maintain, improve, and update it.”* (IDI). Furthermore, implementing a new standard and training employees consumes both human resources and budget – the lack of stable funding creates an immense operational risk: *“If they invest in an open-source project and it collapses in two years, that’s a major issue. If there are suddenly any security issues, where the codebase needs a patch and there is no way to do it quickly, then costs spike dramatically”* (IDI).

The notorious underfunding of the digital commons creates market asymmetry and hinders the scaling of open-source solutions. The primary challenge facing the open source ecosystem worldwide is the lack of a systemic mechanism for funding public assets. Although source code is widely utilized by businesses and administration, this is rarely accompanied by a culture of reciprocity:

“People or institutions using [open source solutions] do not always pitch in. And this is sometimes the reason why there is a reluctance in many companies to open-source things, as in: our competition will use it or take it for free, without contributing anything.” (IDI)

As a result, many key tools are worked on in bursts, outside of regular working hours, drastically limiting their viability in sectors that require immense scaling capital, such as social media platforms.

Widespread risk aversion in mature businesses naturally favors more expensive, centralized consulting firms. Large enterprises thoroughly assess business continuity risks alongside vendor personnel stability. From a corporate perspective, engaging an independent open-source expert is viewed as a potential single point of failure:

“In being involved in a project... if something happens to me, or I stop working with them – well, they are in a bad position. However, they can hire a consulting firm that will take more money, but will have a contract ensuring that even if one consultant drops out, another will step into my place.” (IDI)

From a purely business perspective, **companies prefer to pay significantly more for a recognized brand and the guarantee of continuous vendor support, than to risk cooperating with a dispersed community of developers** – even if the solutions of the latter may be technically superior.

8.4. The Legitimization of Big Tech Monopolies by the State

In the assessment of our interviewees, instead of protecting technological independence, Polish public administration's actions fuel and perpetuate the market monopoly of global corporations. A glaring example of this is the distribution of strategic state applications (e.g., mO-bywatel) exclusively through proprietary, vertically integrated Google and Apple app stores, effectively cutting off market alternatives like SailfishOS, Ubuntu Touch or PostmarketOS⁹⁰. The situation is similar regarding official government communication, which is frequently conducted on privately owned platforms, such as X (formerly Twitter). This practice forces citizens to create accounts and accept commercial privacy policies to gain access to archival public information, which should be openly accessible by law:

"Why does the Polish government publish things on Twitter? Why do Polish public institutions publish certain information only on Twitter? If someone wants to read it, they have to create an account on Elon Musk's private platform, approve his privacy policy, and literally sell their data for that access. This is absurd [...] I am not saying that this data should not be on Twitter, let it be on Twitter, but let it also be in another place that respects the users..." (IDI)

As the interviews conducted for this study indicate, this dominance is directly perpetuated in public procurement through the mass construction of tender specifications by copying and pasting from ready-made terms of reference catalogs. Officials, fearing accusations of public funds mismanagement or procedural errors, prefer to describe contracts in such a way that *"they can only be fulfilled by one specific vendor"* (IDI), thereby eliminating local entities offering open-source solutions from the outset. As one of the experts noted, *"if a state or local government commissions software, then this software should, at the very least, be accessible to the state. The state should also receive the copyright. That is to say, we are not doing vendor lock-in, but the state acquires the source code alongside the right to have it at their disposal"* (IDI). **This situation is exacerbated by the lack of independent, state-funded certification institutions that could alleviate officials' fears regarding open-source software implementation by formally confirming its stability.**

8.5. Not Much Allure

Implementing clean, optimized open-source code loses out to the logic of political marketing. The transition to open-source software is a long-term, technically complex process that is challenging from a perspective of Public Relations and communication with the mainstream recipient.

90 Woźniak M., *Nie ma weryfikacji wieku bez filtrowania internetu*, 2026, <https://rys.io/pl/183.html>.

“When there is such hype, it is hard to break through with such, so to speak, boring things. Because the truth is that often boring things are exactly what we need. It’s just that it won’t gain media traction, you won’t be able to cut a ribbon at a new server room, you won’t be able to create a media buzz around it... so why do it?” (IDI)

Decentralized and grassroots projects suffer from chronic deficiencies in branding and aesthetic quality of their interfaces. **The lack of business-like, client-first thinking means that these systems, although they may be technically excellent, fail completely to compete with their commercial counterparts when it comes to intuitive ease of use for laypeople.**

“Underfunding at the UX/UI level is, so to speak, the Achilles’ heel of open-source projects – and the greatest challenge they face.” (IDI)

8.6. “Open-Washing” and Marketing Misuse

Both corporations and public institutions are increasingly using open-source rhetoric solely as a Public Relations smokescreen, masking solutions bound by restrictive commercial licenses. Experts point directly to the example of PLLuM, the high-profile, publicly funded Polish artificial intelligence project. In practice, the openness declared in the media proves to be partially unfounded:

“We started looking at the licenses and it turned out that it is not entirely open, [...] only the base licenses are based on MIT, and the advanced ones require the consent of some university [...] or are restricted to academic use. This is just another government open-washing.” (IDI)

In this case, the state – instead of building real digital commons – resorts to partially open solutions, presenting them as an example of the Polish administration’s actions to advance open-source software principles. **Such practices cause justified frustration within the community of open-source experts and among tech-savvy consumers, while also lowering public trust in the actions and communications of public administration.**

8.7. Stability in Light of Decentralized Open Source Environment

According to the experts participating in the study, the adoption of open-source solutions is hindered by officials’ fear of losing stability and control – for example, in the event of a system failure. In the commercial world, acquiring software resembles purchasing a physical product at a store: the buyer receives a standardized, proprietary “box” complete with step-by-step instructions. Conversely, **adopting open-source software requires moving beyond the well-**

worn pattern of purchasing licenses toward investing in maintenance and services from local partners. For public administration, this transition can be difficult as it breeds fear that an “informal group of developers” will not guarantee stability. Consequently, public service officials prefer to pay “a premium” to Big Tech corporations so that, in the event of a crisis, they have an external entity onto whom they can shift responsibility, even if that support is illusory.

Furthermore, the Polish open-source community is deeply fragmented, leaving representatives of public administration and central officials to struggle with the lack of a single point of contact or reference:

“Communities often operate on an informal basis, which means there are some local meetups for users of various open-source solutions, or developers specializing in particular projects, or occasional conferences. However, it is all very fragmented. There is no integration, which ties into the problem I mentioned earlier: Perhaps the state or the ministry wants to talk, but they don’t know with whom – they don’t know who to approach? I feel like it’s a bit of a desert when it comes to organization and what is happening in and around this space. There is a clear lack of ‘advocates’ for open source.” (IDI)

9. Conclusions

The transition to free and open source software in Poland presents a strategic opportunity to break free of technological dependence. However, the success of this transformation depends on a well-rounded management strategy and leveraging the synergies among digital sovereignty, cost optimization, public policy support, environmental sustainability, and usability, as well as new models of economic cooperation at various levels.

Thus far, the discussion around OSS in public administration has been stalled by a dilemma built on premises that are not grounded in current reality – such as the fear that funding and releasing source code using public funds is a wasteful practice akin to “giving away for free” the fruits of Polish labor to foreign competition. **In the current proprietary model, Poland spends billions of zlotys every year on foreign solutions, paying “rent” and building the power of global Big Tech corporations, whereas these costs could be transformed into investments in the local economy.** True sovereignty requires reversing this logic and treating technology not as a one-time purchase of a pre-packaged product, but as the living infrastructure of the state and a consistently developed common good.

9.1. Digital Sovereignty as Protection of the Public Interest

The current dependence of Poland’s public institutions – including healthcare, education, and research – on proprietary software increases vulnerability to geopolitical turmoil while generating significant strategic risk in the event of vendor bankruptcy or sudden licensing changes.

Open systems are not inferior to proprietary alternatives from a technical standpoint, and their key systemic advantage is the full auditability of the codebase, which enhances state security. The higher barrier to entry when drafting public procurement contracts, alongside deficiencies in user-friendliness, could similarly be resolved through mature management and systemic support from the central administration. As the study indicates, open-source is primarily a matter of user autonomy – its technical dimension is distinct from actual sovereignty: *“Buying a service on a server that runs on Linux has little to do with the freedom of the user who uses this service – in fact, absolutely nothing at all”* (IDI).

One’s freedom of use should therefore be treated on an equal footing with fundamental civil rights:

“If the topic of freedom of the press, freedom of movement, and freedom of speech is sexy, then the topic of software user freedom is sexy to the exact same extent. [...]

People should be interested in whether the government is, for example, handing over their freedom into the hands of some corporations.” (IDI)

Public funds should finance local solutions and the digital commons (treated as “national goods”, perhaps?), rather than foreign capital:

“Most of the code written by highly talented Polish programmers is simply closed off. It is exported so that an American millionaire can profit from it later, rather than serving Polish sovereignty, advancing innovation, and creating better technologies for users.” (IDI)

Redirecting even a fraction of these budgets could foster exponential growth in the domestic market:

“If at least 10% of what the state spends on Microsoft software were allocated to open-source, over the years we would witness the growth of a remarkable, powerful, and sovereign ecosystem of applications that work better, and over which we actually have control.” (IDI)

This model restores to the user a sense of democratic control and agency, providing a safe space for free innovation rather than confining them to proprietary corporate ecosystems. It is within those ecosystems that, as one of our interviewees notes, “companies use technology to control people, instead of the ideal state where a device is my property and I decide what it can do” (IDI). Furthermore, the use of open standards protects civil liberties; the state then does not confine citizens to purchase tools from a specific vendor, thereby fulfilling its statutory duty to ensure fair competition in public procurement. One’s autonomy remains the ultimate goal:

“We cannot lose sight of the goal. The goal is greater digital sovereignty. The goal is people’s agency and autonomy, which translates into our institutions being less dependent, allowing us to choose the best solutions [...] so that the money stays locally and circulates here. But it all starts with control.” (IDI)

9.2. Cost Effectiveness

An analysis of the Total Cost of Ownership (TCO) clearly shows that the open source model allows for the avoidance of vendor lock-ins and margins imposed by monopolists. The cost of maintaining licenses (such as the commonly used Windows with Office suites) on a single workstation in a public office can reach up to several hundred zlotys per year, whereas in the open model, this cost can drop to zero.

Budget savings, however, do not stem from the software being “free” – open source software requires a reorientation of budgets. Financial benefits become real only when hollow, cyclical license fees are transformed into a targeted investment: in the development, implementation, and maintenance of systems, and in personnel – hiring qualified experts, upskilling public administration representatives, and cooperating with end-users and the open source community. This model is less capital-intensive, though more labor-intensive in the initial phase. Local governments and institutions fund the creation of the tools and functionalities they need only once, obtaining the code for their own use without the necessity of paying for multi-year subscriptions. Redirecting these streams allows public spending to be treated as an instrument of economic development:

“Injecting 10, 20, 30 billion zlotys annually into the economy – and a highly specialized economy at that, which is furthermore spread across the country [...] Small IT companies will be able to provide services, they will be able to grow, and have more stable sources of funding.” (IDI)

It is worth noting that many systems already in use by the Polish government are based on open-source solutions:

“It seems to me that representatives of the Polish administration often do not realize that they are implementing open source. For example, if a data center is being built [...] I’m betting an arm that the overwhelming majority of them operate on some version of Linux, which is an open-source operating system. I think a significant portion of the technology powering the devices they use has open-source roots. [...] They are simply unaware of it.” (IDI)

True optimization requires a systemic reorientation. Currently, this change is spearheaded by small local governments – those hardest hit by budget constraints and the outflow of funds to global intermediary platforms. For them, a viable solution is a digital cooperative model, meaning sharing of resources such as code, digital solutions (platforms, applications), costs of joint infrastructure (servers or cloud services)⁹¹.

9.3. Digital Ecology

Proprietary solutions often overload processors with hidden trackers and aggressive telemetry. The massive digital noise generated by this not only exposes users to data interception or leakage, but also drives unnecessary, continuous energy consumption across Big Tech’s cloud infrastructure. Open-source software offers clean, optimized code designed to run locally:

⁹¹ See also: Jan J. Zygmuntowski, *Wspólnice danych. Alternatywny model zarządzania danymi*, 2020, <https://centrumcyfrowe.pl/spoltech/wspolnice-danych-raport-projektu-spoltech/>

“In the context of open source, you get rid of all that surveillance capitalism and you have a space, an ecosystem that is clean and that does not track your every activity. Because of it, this operational world is smaller because you actually need fewer resources. Applications are lighter, they don’t have such huge requirements. They are designed in such a way as to run locally, instead of Software as a Service, calculated somewhere in the cloud. [...] Because you actually utilize the resources of your computer hardware less and in a more gentle way, you automatically extend the life cycle of your device, since it simply does not get drained. The battery is the hardware component that is most frequently replaced, and when you use less electricity, you need to charge less, you have fewer battery charging cycles used, you take better care of your equipment, and it automatically lasts longer. This footprint, everything related to production – you contribute to reducing it.” (IDI)

For organizations with limited budgets, switching to Linux and regaining unrestricted hardware access – including combating the planned obsolescence driven by proprietary software or locked bootloaders – forms the foundation for protecting user rights and freedoms. **Full transparency also enables informed choices regarding sustainable and/or hosting providers (e.g., through state research institutes, such as NASK), thereby preventing the transfer of data to facilities located outside the European Union.**

10. The Path Forward: Recommendations for Strategy and Implementation

Implementing open-source solutions will bring Poland closer to digital sovereignty – defined as full control and auditability of state systems, rather than an attempt to build everything from scratch. **To break the administration’s reliance on global technology monopolies, the state must reject simulated openness (“open-washing”) and become the legal guarantor of public code.** An essential prerequisite is the application of suitably structured open licenses that will protect publicly funded software from potential corporate re-closure and commercial exploitation.

To overcome the barriers identified in the study and transform open-source software into a driver of Polish economy, in alignment with existing public policy declarations, the state should implement the following mechanisms post haste:

I. **A New Model of Central Administrative Operations: The State as the Host and Architect of the Ecosystem**

The state should shift from being a passive recipient of off-the-shelf technologies or a centralized controller. **The ultimate goal is to assume the role of a moderator and facilitator that focuses on and supports cooperation among various sectors: business, the developer community, and non-governmental organizations.** Utilizing its institutional authority, public administration should host a platform for dialogue, providing local open-source developers and NGOs – which foster debate and capacity building in this area – with the assurance that their voices are heard at the government level. A key element of this role is the sustained funding of information-exchange forums, training programs, and inter-ministerial and local government conferences. This will facilitate an organic exchange of both “hard” implementation data and actual budget savings, as well as shared experiences and best practices.

Viable next steps:

Central Deployment Platform (Base of Evidence)

The state (e.g., through the Ministry of Digital Affairs) should consider launching a nationwide registry of open-source deployments used within public administration. This portal should aggregate Total Cost of Ownership (TCO) calculations, technical specifications, maintenance service agreement templates, and risk analyses from completed projects. Consequently, those planning a migration would not have to devote their budget for in-depth legal or technical analyses from scratch, nor spend time obtaining data through public records requests; instead, they could simply download a pre-verified “evidence package” compiled by other institutions.

Incubation of the local market of services (commercial OSS ecosystem)

The state’s role as a facilitator must involve fostering an economic environment conducive to the emergence and development of new, domestic technology companies specializing in hosting, maintaining, and servicing open-source solutions. Through targeted accelerator programs and the public procurement system, the state possesses the levers to stimulate the creation of niche software houses, local cloud providers, and digital cooperatives. These entities can gradually assume the role of guarantors of system stability, providing a secure deployment alternative. In this manner, public funds wouldn’t permanently flow out of the domestic economic circulation, but would instead be reinvested locally, creating high-quality job opportunities and building capacity in the area of digital sovereignty.

Knowledge exchange and capacity building

Financial resources should be allocated to personnel – specifically regional teams of engineers and deployment specialists operating under a training micro-grant framework. Rather than theoretical lectures, peer site visits and hands-on workshops should be funded. Practitioners from local governments who have demonstrated experience in deploying OSS and OSH, should be provided means and space to support neighboring municipalities, co-configuring systems and resolving compatibility issues alongside local IT personnel. At the same time, targeted funds should cover training in change management, safeguarding middle and senior management against cognitive resistance and apprehension toward new technological solutions.

Inclusive consultations around OSS, with partner-based engagement of all stakeholders

Public and technical consultation processes should be designed with appropriate lead time, enabling the meaningful engagement of a broad spectrum of experts. Panels and workshops require a hybrid format and a predictable schedule to accommodate the resource constraints of smaller entities, independent specialists, and organizations based outside the capital city.

Regional digital diplomacy (cooperation in the region)

Instead of operating in isolation, Poland should deepen its involvement in the international exchange of knowledge and build a strong position in the Central and Eastern European region.

The first step should be the systematic and strategic integration of domestic institutions and universities into existing European initiatives, alongside the initiation of new regional partnerships.

II. Public Code, Public Good: A Change of Approach in Public Procurement

Implementing the “Public Money, Public Code” principle by introducing a statutory obligation modeled on the demands of the Free Software Foundation Europe⁹² would require all software ordered and financed with public funds to be made available under a free software license. This framework safeguards the state’s economic copyright and ensures unrestricted access to the source code, along with the right to freely dispose of it. Legislative precedents – such as the 2016 French law mandating OSS usage to preserve the control and independence of IT systems⁹³, and the 2012 Italian regulation establishing open-source software as the default solution⁹⁴ – should serve as blueprints for the foundation of future Polish legislation in this domain.

Viable next steps:

Antitrust Safeguards and TCO Protection:

In response to the fact that nearly 99% of analyzed public procurement contracts directly or indirectly exclude alternatives to Microsoft products⁹⁵, the implementation of protective mechanisms is imperative.

- **Elimination of hidden favoritism:** A strict ban must be introduced on drafting tender documentation (terms of reference) in a manner that favors one specific commercial vendor, without objective technical justification.
- **Provisions for escaping vendor lock-in:** A mandatory requirement should be introduced to include clauses in proprietary software contracts that guarantee unconditional, cost-free data migration to alternative environments upon contract termination.

Non-price criteria for local providers

It is recommended that bid evaluation frameworks assign a minimum weight of 10% to the organizational status of cooperatives and digital cooperatives, while awarding additional points for offering open-source solutions. This mechanism will help retain capital within the region, and reduce long-term system maintenance costs.

⁹² Free Software Foundation Europe, *Public Money? Public Code!*, <https://fsfe.org/activities/publiccode/publiccode.en.html>.

⁹³ Labo Société Numérique (Agence Nationale de la Cohésion des Territoires), *Free and open source software in France: where do we stand?*, 2022, <https://labo.societenumerique.gouv.fr/en/articles/dossier-free-and-open-source-software-in-france-where-are-we/>.

⁹⁴ European Commission (Open Source Observatory – OSOR), *Italian military to switch to LibreOffice and ODF*, 2015, <https://interoperable-europe.ec.europa.eu/collection/open-source-observatory-osor/news/italian-military-switch>.

⁹⁵ J. Kopeć, *Zamówienia na pozór otwarte. Nierówne szanse producentów oprogramowania w zamówieniach publicznych polskiej administracji*, 2025, <https://instrat.pl/zamowienia-na-pozor-otwarte/>.

Central Procurement Template Database

The Public Procurement Office should develop standardized, legally verified terms of reference templates based on alternative and open-source solutions. This will provide officials within smaller, local government units with a solid legal foundation and a sense of security, protecting them from decision paralysis, allegations of public funds misuse, or the habitual reflex to purchase proprietary systems rather than conducting an objective assessment of market realities and organizational needs.

Deployment sandbox for local governments

The central administration can launch a pilot program for migrating to open-source solutions across several pilot municipalities. The deployment of cloud systems and office suites funded by EU funds (such as the National Recovery Plan) will be documented as certified operational guidelines. This will enable other local governments to safely replicate proven, standardized procedures, thereby significantly mitigating the risk of procedural errors.

III. Infrastructure of Trust and National Security

Public Code Repository and Secure OSS Certificate

The state should establish a trusted platform to aggregate key open-source projects ready for direct deployment within public administration. A key element of this solution should be the introduction of a system-wide certification mechanism based on source-code audits conducted by specialized state institutions. The result of this initiative will be an official Secure Open-Source Software Certificate – a state “seal of approval” that will provide officials with certainty that they are deploying stable, proven, and secure solutions, eliminating the need to conduct independent, costly expert assessments.

State system of Open-Source Expert Certification

Establishing an official, state-certified examination system for IT specialists in the field of open-source technologies – recognized within public procurement frameworks – will allow OSS engineers to formally validate their expertise. This initiative will facilitate personnel verification in public tenders and recruitment, elevate the professional standing of experts working with open-source software, and chart a clear career development path within Poland.

Public Maintenance Fund – stability and support for the Polish open source market

A targeted funding program should be established to ensure the maintenance and continuous development of existing code that holds critical operational value for the administration. This fund will provide direct support to:

1. **Domestic technology companies**, which will secure contracts for optimization, bug-fixing, maintenance, and the adaptation of open-source software to the Polish regulatory framework;

2. **Public institutions**, by ensuring long-lasting stability, systemic business continuity, and the assurance that critical digital commons will not be abandoned.

Neutral access to public information: protecting citizens' rights and data

The state must follow a principle of absolute informational neutrality. Key central and local government communications must not be distributed exclusively through private, proprietary social media platforms. The state is obliged to guarantee citizens access to public information without forcing them to "sell" their personal data, undergo profiling, or accept the terms and conditions of foreign corporations. Official communication channels must be built upon open standards and an independent state infrastructure.

IV. The Research Sector and Local Governments as Laboratories of Digital Cooperation

Open Science as a vanguard of change

Since the research sector in Poland is primarily publicly funded, a standardized openness requirement should be introduced: *"what we produce should later be publicly available via open access [...] everything that researchers produce should be as open as possible"* (IDI). The scientific community should serve as a leader and a blueprint for implementing open solutions across other sectors of the economy. Concurrently, this initiative would strengthen civic access to knowledge and reliable research, which is invaluable to safeguarding the right to education and combating disinformation.

Liberating the education system from corporate monopolies

A comprehensive reform of IT curricula is required. Instructions taught in schools and universities must not focus exclusively on Microsoft or Google products. The education provided must encompass universal and platform-neutral concepts: *"If [the school] teaches how to use software, meaning when pupils learn to use a spreadsheet or something, it should not be Excel. It must be explicitly stated and shown that there are alternatives"* (IDI). This will enable consumers to make more informed decisions, foster critical thinking skills and technological awareness among future generations, and introduce them to the concept of the digital commons, whose code can be safely analyzed from within – and, of course, co-created.

Formalizing openness in knowledge institutions

The establishment of both an Open Science Plenipotentiary and an Open Source Data Steward must be made mandatory across all research institutes and universities. This role – which integrates research, legal, programming, and archival or library expertise – will be responsible for identifying and recommending open-source solutions to researchers, standardizing processes, and facilitating the creation of data management plans.

Statutory mandate for sharing local government code in an open source model

A principle must be introduced, requiring that all software, applications, or systems intended for local government entities and financed – even partially – with public funds be made available under a recognized open-source license. This mechanism will eliminate the costly and redundant practice whereby hundreds of municipalities independently pay different vendors to develop identical tools, without fully leveraging their economic copyright: *“Take a simple waste-sorting application – each local government implements it independently, whereas this is something that could be done once, made open-source, and reused multiple times”* (IDI). The new regulation will obligate local governments to publish the source code of developed tools in a publicly accessible repository. Under the open source model, smaller municipalities will no longer need to build systems from scratch or purchase expensive, proprietary licenses – instead, they can simply download the standardized code, allowing domestic IT companies to seamlessly deploy, adapt, and maintain it at the regional level, thereby significantly reducing the cost of the country’s digital transformation.

Implementing this radical mechanism may raise natural market and systemic concerns, which, however, find a simple, pragmatic solution in the open-source model:

Argument: The “freeloader effect” (a Polish municipality pays, while others use it for free)

Counterargument: Under copyleft licenses (e.g., EUPL or GNU GPL; see also: [2.3. Open Licenses and Access](#)), anyone who modifies and improves the code is legally obligated to share their changes under the same license. Therefore, if Municipality X pays for the base application, and a wealthier City Y downloads this solution and adds three new modules to it, Municipality X (and the country as a whole) receives these improvements without incurring additional costs. Code sharing is not a one-sided donation – rather, it represents the construction of a synergistic network in which an entity’s investment returns to the system and yields dividends. Rather than viewing openness as a loss of control or potential profit, it must be accepted that the current “closed” proprietary model generates immense waste in the management of public funds. This inefficiency stems from disparate administrative offices repeatedly procuring identical functionalities. Consolidating expenditure at the national or EU level yields significant savings, while sharing code eliminates the problem of being a “perpetual tenant.”

Argument 2: “The demise of Polish companies dependent on license sales”

Counterargument: The transition to the open-source model does not undermine the Polish IT sector; rather, it shifts the market paradigm toward a more resilient and equitable one. Instead of selling “pre-packaged”, proprietary software and extracting economic rents solely from licensing fees, domestic companies will compete on the quality of implementation, systems integration, consulting, and local support services (SLAs).

V. Professionalization of the Narrative and Strategic Focus of the Open-Source Community

Creators of free and open source software often rely on ideological arguments (such as software freedom, transparency, and ethics) – however, these are secondary concerns for officials responsible for budgets and compliance with public fund management legislation. The Polish open-source community should therefore broaden its discourse to include business and legal arguments, particularly regarding the protection of personal data and sensitive information. When engaging with officials, it is crucial to leverage frameworks such as Total Cost of Ownership (TCO), cybersecurity, regulatory compliance, and risk management. Developing concrete financial calculators and comprehensive procurement guides will help overcome administrative resistance to deploying open-source software.

As this study's in-depth interviews demonstrate, Poland lacks a high-profile, large-scale OSS success story that would serve as a recognizable model for building trust in these types of solutions. Despite the immense potential of domestic open-source developers, the fragmented community creates a multitude of small, scattered tools that quickly languish due to a lack of funding and long-term maintenance. Instead of dissipating its efforts, the community should consider consolidating its initiatives around a few key solutions. Establishing the necessary conditions for these projects to achieve the highest standard of institutional maturity, developing clear governance structures (including a central point of contact), and creating universal integration standards – for instance, with the national login system – will facilitate a secure, large-scale migration to open-source solutions within public administration, while providing other market participants with valuable arguments in favor of free- and open-source software.

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12. About the Report

Abstract

In this report, we analyze the Polish open source ecosystem within the framework of digital sovereignty and innovation that stimulates the domestic economy. Currently, commercial entities and the public administration are heavily dependent on the proprietary solutions of global corporations. This creates severe geopolitical dependencies, threats to citizen data security, and systemic vendor lock-in. Although open-source software forms the foundation of modern digital infrastructure and drives the development of artificial intelligence, Polish initiatives remain fragmented – a phenomenon we call the “archipelago effect.” Additionally, official declarations from decision-makers often bear the hallmarks of superficial open-washing.

Drawing on desk research and in-depth interviews with 15 experts, this study identifies the key barriers to the development of free software and its underlying developer community. These include entrenched mindsets, market asymmetry favoring Big Tech, misaligned Total Cost of Ownership (TCO) structures, and the underfunding and fragmentation of development communities. To overcome these barriers, we propose strategic implementation recommendations, such as introducing the “public money, public code” principle, establishing a Public Code Repository, and launching state maintenance funds for the digital commons. We also recommend liberating IT education from corporate monopolies, fostering digital cooperation among local governments, and stimulating the domestic IT services market. These measures have the potential to permanently bolster Poland’s technological autonomy and security.

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Centrum Cyfrowe Foundation

Centrum Cyfrowe Foundation is a think-and-do-tank that is dedicated to the social dimension of new technologies. Centrum's primary area of interest is the digital dimension of public affairs in Poland, specifically, the analysis of social, cultural, and economic changes related to digital technology. We support the openness of science and culture, work toward social change using digital tools and collaboration models based on sharing resources and knowledge.

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